

SINGLE-SHOT TRANSIENT IMAGING VIA COMPRESSED TIME-OF-FLIGHT IMAGING AND DICTIONARY LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

In this work, we propose a single-shot transient imaging framework that combines sparsity-based signal modeling with compressive frequency-domain sampling. The temporal response function of a scene encodes rich information about depth and light transport, and its accurate reconstruction is critical for various imaging applications. To enable transient recovery from a limited number of measurements, we exploit learned sparse representations in an optimized dictionary basis. We compare multiple sampling strategies in the frequency domain and show that both transient profiles and depth maps can be reconstructed under highly compressed acquisition. Notably, we achieve full transient reconstruction using only 16 modulation frequencies, based on real correlation functions, enabling practical single-shot acquisition through spatial frequency multiplexing.

Index Terms— single-shot, multifrequency, time-of-flight, depth imaging, transient imaging, compressive sensing, dictionary learning.

1. INTRODUCTION

Transient imaging captures the temporal profile of light transport in a scene at high temporal resolution, enabling access to rich information about depth, material, and scene geometry and reflectance. By resolving the scene’s response to a short illumination pulse as a function of time, transient imaging systems surpass conventional intensity or phase-based measurements, providing capabilities essential for applications such as non-line-of-sight imaging, material classification, and light-path analysis.

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Time-of-Flight (ToF) cameras provide a compact and cost-effective platform for transient acquisition [1]. Operating through amplitude-modulated continuous-wave (AMCW) illumination, these systems infer scene depth by analyzing the phase delay between emitted and received signals. While conventional ToF systems are designed to retrieve a single depth value per pixel, the full transient response is encoded in the scene’s frequency-dependent response across multiple modulations. Recovering this high-dimensional signal from a few measurements remains a central challenge, particularly under constraints imposed by bandwidth, integration time, and sensor resolution. While attaining transient imaging with picosecond resolution would require using streak cameras in combination with ultrafast laser sources, as demonstrated in [2], PMD sensors offer a low-cost compact alternative [1], but require the sequential acquisition of raw data at a large number of frequencies and phase shifts, yielding exorbitant acquisition times. Alternatively, sharp correlation functions can be attained using coded demodulation [3]. However, this requires dense sampling at many time delays to acquire full transient profiles. Recent methods using neural network models hold potential for reducing the required data volume for transient reconstruction from ToF data, but at the cost of imposing analytic transient models, e. g., a two-sparse signal in [4], or the sum of a 1-sparse signal and a Weibull distribution, for the direct and global components, respectively, in [5].

The key difficulty in transient reconstruction lies in the sparsity and complexity of the temporal response. Multipath interference (MPI), where photons traverse multiple paths before reaching the detector, leads to ambiguous phase readings and degraded depth accuracy. This motivates approaches that explicitly model the transient as a sparse signal composed of a few dominant light paths. If such a sparse representation exists in an appropriate basis or dictionary, it opens the door for compressive sensing (CS) formulations that allow non-parametric recovery of the full transient from significantly fewer measurements than what traditional Nyquist sampling dictates.

We adopt and extend this sparse modeling paradigm, building upon the work [6], which demonstrated the efficacy of learned dictionaries for transient reconstruction from

frequency-modulated ToF measurements. We employ adapted learned dictionaries for low-frequency measurements by introducing an additional sparsification step that enforces structured sparsity within the dictionary atoms themselves. By assigning different support sizes across subsets of atoms, we construct dictionaries with support-restricted (SR) elements that better capture the diversity of temporal structures in transient responses. This structure-aware formulation not only reduces reconstruction error, especially in low-frequency measurement regimes but also promotes robustness to noise and MPI distortions.

Moreover, by casting the inverse problem in a compressive sensing framework, we revisit the frequency-domain sampling design. Our acquisition scheme is optimal since it explicitly maximizes the incoherence between the sensing matrix (derived from the Fourier-modulated ToF responses) and the signal's representation basis (dictionary learned from the training data). This optimal sampling procedure ensures that even a small set of frequency measurements suffices for accurate reconstruction. We validate this approach by reconstructing full transient signals using only 16 frequency components, experimentally acquired by a system with spatially multiplexed modulation patterns. Our system leverages ultrashort illumination pulses and a novel frequency multiplexing strategy across the sensor's pixel array [7], enabling transient imaging at high temporal resolution without requiring sequential scanning or multiple exposures.

We validate our method using a combination of experimental measurements and transient data from [8], demonstrating single-shot transient reconstruction using only 16 frequency-modulated samples. This work presents a principled and scalable solution for transient imaging in resource-constrained ToF systems, setting the stage for future advances in snapshot ultrafast imaging and compact light-transport diagnostics [3].

2. METHODOLOGY

This section presents the sensing model for our continuous-wave (CW) ToF system, describes the learning of sparse representations using structured dictionaries, and formulates the inverse reconstruction problem within a CS framework for recovering transient and depth information from limited frequency measurements.

2.1. Fourier-Domain Sensing Model

In CW indirect ToF (iToF) cameras, as used in our setup, the measurement at a single ToF pixel can be modeled as:

$$y(\tau) = h_{\text{cam}} * h_{\text{sce}}(\tau), \quad (1)$$

where $h_{\text{cam}}(t)$ is the camera's temporal response, and $h_{\text{sce}}(t)$ is the Scene Response Function (SRF) or transient response from the scene. The goal of ToF imaging is to recover the SRF, which characterizes the reflected light signal received at each pixel. In the simplest case involving a single reflection, this response is

effectively 1-sparse. However, in more general scenarios, where multiple light paths reach the sensor due to MPI, the signal becomes K -sparse. It can be simplified as a weighted sum of K time-shifted Dirac delta functions, each corresponding to a distinct path with a unique delay and amplitude:

$$h(t) = \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} \Gamma_k \delta(t - t_k), \quad t_k = \frac{2d_k}{c}, \quad (2)$$

where t_k represents the round-trip time delay associated with the k -th reflection, Γ_k denotes its amplitude, d_k is the corresponding distance, and c is the speed of light. By estimating the time delays t_k , the distance of each reflection can be computed, accounting for the round-trip travel of the light signal. On the other hand, the CW-iToF camera's response function can be modulated as:

$$h_{\text{cam},k}(t; \phi) = A \cos(2\pi f_k t - \phi), \quad (3)$$

where A is the amplitude, f_k is the k -th modulation frequency, and ϕ is a phase shift. Acquiring data at $\phi = 0$ and $\phi = \frac{\pi}{2}$ yields real and imaginary parts of the Fourier coefficient $F_{f_k}(h_{\text{sce}})$. Discretizing $h_{\text{sce}}(t)$ over a fine temporal grid of step size t_{step} leads to a vector $\vec{h}_{\text{sce}} \in \mathbb{R}^n$, with $T = nt_{\text{step}}$. The measurements can then be expressed as:

$$y_k^{\text{R}} = \vec{x}_k^{\text{R}\top} \vec{h}_{\text{sce}}, \quad \text{with} \quad \vec{x}_k^{\text{R}}[n_0] = A \cos(2\pi f_k n_0 t_{\text{step}}), \quad (4)$$

$$y_k^{\text{I}} = \vec{x}_k^{\text{I}\top} \vec{h}_{\text{sce}}, \quad \text{with} \quad \vec{x}_k^{\text{I}}[n_0] = A \sin(2\pi f_k n_0 t_{\text{step}}). \quad (5)$$

Stacking measurements across K frequencies yields the combined sensing model:

$$\vec{y} = \mathbf{x} \vec{h}_{\text{sce}}, \quad \text{with} \quad \mathbf{x} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}^{\text{R}} \\ \mathbf{x}^{\text{I}} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{x}^{\text{R}} = \begin{bmatrix} \vec{x}_1^{\text{R}\top} \\ \vdots \\ \vec{x}_K^{\text{R}\top} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{x}^{\text{I}} = \begin{bmatrix} \vec{x}_1^{\text{I}\top} \\ \vdots \\ \vec{x}_K^{\text{I}\top} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

In practice, n is large (high depth resolution and long range), but $2K \ll n$ because it is determined by the frame rate in mono-frequency systems, rendering the system under-determined.

2.2. Learning Sparse Signal Representations

We assume that transient signals possess bounded complexity and can be sparsely expressed in a suitable dictionary. Let $\{\vec{\psi}_i\}_{i=1}^N \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be a dictionary where $N > n$, forming an over-complete basis. The scene response \vec{h}_{sce} is assumed to admit a sparse representation:

$$\vec{y} = \mathbf{X} \vec{h}_{\text{sce}} = \mathbf{X} \Psi \vec{s} = \mathbf{A} \vec{s}, \quad \text{with} \quad (7)$$

$$\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{X} \Psi, \quad \Psi = [\vec{\psi}_1, \dots, \vec{\psi}_N]$$

Let $\mathbf{H}_{\text{sce}} = [\vec{h}_{\text{sce},1}, \dots, \vec{h}_{\text{sce},M}] \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times M}$ be a collection of M training samples. We learn Ψ and the corresponding sparse

coefficients $\mathbf{S} = [\vec{s}_1, \dots, \vec{s}_M]$ by solving:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\Psi}, \hat{\mathbf{S}} &= \arg \min_{\Psi, \mathbf{S}} \|\mathbf{H}_{\text{sce}} - \Psi \mathbf{S}\|_F^2, \\ \text{s.t.} \quad &\begin{cases} \|\vec{s}_i\|_0 \leq \kappa_{\max}, & \forall i \\ \|\vec{\psi}_j\|_0 \leq \eta_{\max}^j, & \forall j \end{cases}, \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where $\|\cdot\|_F$ is the Frobenius norm, and κ_{\max} is the sparsity constraint and η_{\max}^j is an upper bound on the sparsity of the j^{th} dictionary atoms. In other words, we extend the sparse dictionary learning formulation originally considered in [6] to simultaneously enforce sparse atoms and sparse representation coefficients. More specifically, we divide the atom space in sets of dyadically-decaying size, \mathcal{S}_q , and enforce the same $\eta_{\max}^j = \eta_{\max}^{\mathcal{S}_q} \forall j \in \mathcal{S}_q$, where the following power law is implemented to increase the allowed atom sparsity with q : $\eta_{\max}^{\mathcal{S}_q} = (\eta_{\max}^{\mathcal{S}_1})^q$. Furthermore, atom sparsity is forced to be structural for realism, that is, $\text{supp}(\vec{\psi}_j)$ is forced to be a simply connected set when enforcing sparsity of $\vec{\psi}_j, \forall j$. To solve (8), we consider the following algorithmic procedures: Method of Optimal Directions (MOD) [9], K-SVD [10], approximate K-SVD [11], Online Dictionary Learning (ODL) [12], and Reweighted Least Squares Dictionary Learning (RLS-DLA) [13]. In all cases except for ODL, we extend the original formulation with an additional sparsity-inducing step right after the dictionary updates. For ODL, we make use of a built-in option in the SPAMS library that allows regularizing the atoms with the additional constraint $(1 - \gamma_1) \|d_j\|_2^2 + \gamma_1 \|d_j\|_1 \leq 1$. All methods are initialized with the same frame, and Orthogonal Matching Pursuit (OMP) is used both for sparse coding and for the sparsity-inducing step of all methods except ODL. For the built-in ODL regularizer, we set $\gamma_1 = 0.125$.

2.3. Compressive Transient Reconstruction Model

Once the dictionary $\hat{\Psi}$ is learned, we can recover the sparse code \vec{s} from the measurements \vec{y} by solving:

$$\hat{\vec{s}} = \arg \min_{\vec{s}} \|\vec{s}\|_0 \quad \text{s.t.} \quad \vec{y} = \mathbf{A}\vec{s}. \quad (9)$$

Once $\hat{\vec{s}}$ is estimated (using OMP), we recover the transient signal from $\hat{h}_{\text{sce}} = \hat{\Psi}\hat{\vec{s}}$. The depth estimate is then computed using peak detection on \hat{h}_{sce} :

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{d} &= \frac{c}{2}(\hat{n}_0 \cdot t_{\text{step}}), \quad \text{where} \quad \hat{n}_0 = \arg \max_{n_0} \hat{h}_{\text{sce}}[n_0] \\ &\text{s.t.} \quad \hat{h}_{\text{sce}}[n_0] > \epsilon, \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where ϵ is a signal threshold. To address multipath interference and edge artifacts, multiple peaks may be considered.

3. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

To evaluate our transient reconstruction framework, we perform experiments using both experimental and synthetic data. We

Fig. 1: Photograph of the measurement setup including iToF 3D imager with illumination module.

assess dictionary learning methods under a highly undersampled setting with 16 frequency-modulated measurements. We analyze the accuracy of transient and depth reconstruction, dictionary training performance, and depth recovery under various sampling strategies.

Fig. 1 illustrates our novel experimental setup for 3D ranging. The illumination module comprises a high-current driver capable of generating high-peak-power light pulses with adjustable pulse widths in the nanosecond range, and a high-power Vertical-Cavity Surface-Emitting Laser (VCSEL) operating in the near-infrared (NIR) spectrum. On the receiver side, the system includes an iToF camera with programmable CW modulation. An objective lens ($f=8\text{mm}$, $F/1.4$) and an NIR optical filter are mounted in front of the camera lens.

To construct the training matrix $\mathbf{H}_{\text{sce}} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times M}$, we use 25 transient images from the *iToF2dToF* dataset [8], which contains high-resolution temporal responses of various indoor scenes. Each transient signal consists of $n = 2000$ samples, acquired with a step size of $t_{\text{step}} = 33.333$ ps, covering a total duration of $T = 66.666$ ns. This corresponds to an unambiguous depth range of approximately 7.5 m, matching the range of a 20 MHz modulation. Each image spans 120×160 pixels, yielding about 1.92×10^4 transient profiles per scene. Following [8], we use 21 scenes for training and reserve four for validation and testing. From over 4×10^5 available profiles, we randomly select $M = 10^5$ to build the training matrix. Dictionaries $\Psi \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times N}$ are trained using five dictionary learning algorithms, as outlined in Section 2, with $N = 8000$ atoms, resulting in an overcompleteness factor of 4.

3.1. Sparse Representation of Transient Profiles

Fig. 2 shows the measured cross-correlation functions, captured using the proposed setup configured to acquire modulation frequencies from 2 MHz to 32 MHz. They are acquired from the central pixel of the sensor array while a white diffusing target is placed at a distance of 50 cm in front of the sensor and illuminated by the pulsed VCSEL source. The demodulation signal is sequentially delayed in 1 ns increments relative to the emitted light pulse, enabling coverage of the full period of the base modulation frequency of 2 MHz. An exposure time of 50 ms per

Table 1: Normalized sparse reconstruction RMSE and training time for each SR dictionary learning method.

Method	SR-MOD	SR-K-SVD	SR-Approx-K-SVD	SR-ODL	SR-RLS-DLA
Training RMSE (a.u.)	2.431×10^{-2}	3.916×10^{-2}	1.292×10^{-2}	1.911×10^{-2}	83.729×10^{-2}
Time (s)	1.719×10^4	1.308×10^4	9.464×10^3	1.001×10^3	4.5188×10^4

Fig. 2: Experimentally measured cross-correlation functions captured using the proposed setup for 16 frequencies.

frame is used, yielding a depth image frame rate of 2 fps, currently limited by the data transfer bandwidth between the FPGA and the host computer. For each delay step, responses are averaged over 50 consecutive frames. The experimental correlation functions are acquired sequentially for 16 modulation frequencies, while the illumination system emits identical light pulses.

Training is performed only on valid pixels of the dataset with sufficient signal energy, and sparse codes are computed using OMP with a sparsity constraint of $\kappa_{\max} = 16$. Table 1 shows the normalized sparse reconstruction RMSE and training time for each SR method. Compared to the RMSE values reported in [6], our SR dictionaries achieve comparable reconstruction error and computational cost. This demonstrates the effectiveness of enforcing structured sparsity during dictionary learning, especially in compressive transient imaging scenarios.

We reconstruct transient profiles following the methodology described in Section 2. To emulate transient measurements, we convolve experimentally measured cross-correlation functions with per-pixel transient profiles from the *iToF2dToF* dataset [8]. To ensure proper alignment, the experimental signals are interpolated and upsampled to match the temporal resolution and step size of the dataset profiles. This enables consistent sampling and reconstruction across all scenes. Figure 3 shows reconstructed transients for two representative pixels (columns) using all five dictionary learning methods from [6] and their corresponding SR versions (rows). All methods closely match the ground truth in most cases, with the exception of RLS-DLA. The noisy behavior observed in this method has been omitted for one pixel (first column) to enhance visual clarity. As seen, SR dictionaries generally provide more accurate reconstructions (e.g., second column), particularly in terms of peak localization. In several cases, the second peak aligns more

Fig. 3: Examples of transients for two pixels reconstructed using all dictionary learning methods (top) and their corresponding SR versions (bottom).

Table 2: Percentile depth MAE and execution time for the SR-MOD dictionary using three sparse recovery algorithms: OMP, BP, and BPDN. Results are reported for *kitchen-2*.

Method	Depth MAE per Percentile (mm)				Time (s)
	0-75%	75-85%	85-95%	95-99%	
OMP	11.40	40.00	58.50	93.47	8.53×10^1
BP	10.34	40.07	57.47	93.06	4.06×10^2
BPDN	10.34	40.07	57.47	93.06	3.99×10^2

closely with the true depth, highlighting the benefit of structured sparsity in capturing multipath components.

3.2. Depth Retrieval from Transient Profiles

To evaluate the impact of the sparse solver on reconstruction accuracy and efficiency, we tested three common recovery algorithms, OMP, Basis Pursuit (BP), and Basis Pursuit Denoising (BPDN) [14, 15], using SR-MOD. Table 2 summarizes the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) over different error percentiles for scene *kitchen-2* from the *iToF2dToF* dataset and the total execution time required for each solver. All methods used 16 frequency-modulated measurements. Results show that while OMP offers faster inference, BP and BPDN yield slightly improved accuracy. These results highlight the trade-off between computational efficiency and reconstruction fidelity in solving this sparse inverse problem.

We also evaluated the mutual coherence between the sensing matrix \mathbf{X} and the dictionary Ψ , as well as the reconstruction performance of the learned dictionaries and their SR versions. Table 3 summarizes both the mutual coherence values and the depth MAE across different error percentiles for the *kitchen-2*

Table 3: Mutual coherence between the sensing matrix \mathbf{X} and the dictionary Ψ , along with percentile depth MAE for trained dictionaries and their SR versions for *kitchen-2* scene.

Dict. Learn. Method	Mutual Coherence \mathbf{X}, Ψ	Depth MAE per Percentile (mm)			
		0-75%	75-85%	85-95%	95-99%
MOD	0.8694	14.76	50.45	67.20	112.11
SR-MOD	0.8179	11.40	40.00	58.50	93.47
K-SVD	0.7836	13.93	45.51	68.02	113.36
SR-K-SVD	0.3665	13.69	43.26	65.60	106.33
App-K-SVD	0.8115	62.55	162.07	467.76	577.95
SR-App-K-SVD	0.6201	16.61	48.31	70.82	108.86
ODL	0.9841	143.60	368.52	433.85	471.80
SR-ODL	0.4443	8.69	34.49	56.14	107.34
RLS-DLA	0.5616	143.60	368.52	433.85	471.80
SR-RLS-DLA	0.1348	395.02	610.58	653.71	689.32

Fig. 4: Depth reconstructions from the best-performing methods and their error maps for the *living-Room-2* and *kitchen-2* scenes from the *iToF2dToF* dataset. All scales are in meters.

scene from the *iToF2dToF* dataset. All methods were evaluated using 16 frequency-modulated measurements. The results confirm the effectiveness of SR dictionary learning in improving reconstruction performance in compressive transient imaging. Among the tested methods, SR-MOD, SR-K-SVD, and SR-ODL achieve the best overall performance. The SR variant of K-SVD shows results comparable to its original version, while SR-RLS-DLA performs worse, likely due to reduced flexibility in adapting to the data under support constraints.

Fig. 4 presents depth reconstructions and corresponding error maps for the *living-Room-2* and *kitchen-2* scenes from the *iToF2dToF* dataset. The SR-MOD and SR-ODL dictionaries yield notably lower reconstruction errors among the tested approaches, while the RLS-DLA shows a poor performance.

3.3. Compressive Fourier-Domain Transient Recovery

To investigate how the number of measurements affects reconstruction accuracy, we evaluate the evolution of the depth MAE with respect to the sampling ratio $\delta = m/n$, where m is the

Fig. 5: Depth MAE vs. sampling ratio $\delta = m/n$ for scene *kitchen-2*. Results are shown for different learned dictionaries.

Fig. 6: Depth MAE vs. relative sparsity ratio $\rho = s/m$, with fixed $m = 20$, for scene *kitchen-2*. Color coding as in Fig. 5.

number of measurements and n is the length of the transient signal. Fig. 5 shows this behavior for scene *kitchen-2*, using different dictionaries for uniform, random sampling on a grid, random, and sparse ruler Fourier sampling methods. In the random sampling strategy, a subset of frequency channels is selected uniformly at random from the total set of measurements. For the sparse ruler strategy, we employ a fixed, predefined sparse ruler pattern, without performing any optimization. As observed in Fig. 5, the best-performing method approaches near-zero error with the random sampling on a grid and sparse ruler, while this is not the case for the uniform sampling.

To assess the reconstruction limits under fixed measurement constraints, we examine the impact of the sparsity-to-measurement ratio $\rho = s/m$ on depth accuracy. Fig. 6 presents the depth MAE for scene *kitchen-2* as ρ increases, while the number of measurements is fixed at $m = 20$ ($\delta = 0.01$). Coherently with [6], the results show that all sampling schemes maintain robust reconstruction performance even at high relative sparsity levels.

4. CONCLUSION

We proposed a single-shot transient imaging framework that reconstructs temporal light transport using only 16 frequency measurements. By combining learned sparse representations with optimized dictionary structure and sampling design, our method enables accurate transient and depth recovery from highly compressed data. Experimental results validate its effectiveness across various sampling strategies. Despite performing well in sparse and moderately complex scenes, MPI remains challenging under limited measurements. Addressing this will require broader bandwidths and denser sampling. Future work will explore adaptive strategies and hardware enhancements to improve MPI retrieval in real-time scenarios.

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